

**Wall Fracturing versus Mechanical Instability as Competing Intrusion Mechanisms of Dikes:
Insights from Laboratory Experiments**

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Introduction

This is the supporting information used to develop the present manuscript.

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15 **Text S1. Regional structural evolution**

16 On a regional scale, the rocks of Chotonagpur Granite Gneissic Complex underwent ductile
17 deformations (Sanyal & Sengupta, 2020) due to an overall tectonic north-to-south movement in the
18 terrain. The deformations have resulted in the development of penetrative fabrics in the country
19 rocks. In places, the fabrics have been folded by later deformation. The terrain has been intruded by
20 pegmatites that show cross-cutting relations with the regional fabrics.

21

22 **Text S2. Field documentation**

23 We prepared high resolution (scale in order of 1:100) plain paper maps in two selective
24 locations of the south-east CGGC (Fig. 8a) to study the geometrical patterns of pegmatite
25 emplacement and other granitic bodies in the gneissic country rocks. The locations were Balakdih
26 ($23^{\circ}12.8264'N$, $86^{\circ}31.029'E$), and Chakultar ($23^{\circ}14.258'N$, $86^{\circ}21.764'E$), Purulia district, West Bengal.
27 Both locations display excellent exposures of granite pegmatites of multiple generations intruded
28 into the granite gneiss.

29 The study areas show gneissic foliations defined by alternate banding of felsic quartzo-
30 feldspathic and mafic biotite or amphibolite material segregation. Some of the pegmatitic layers are
31 almost parallel to, and some are crosscutting the major gneissic foliation (Fig. 8b). A dominant set
32 of thick (thickness varies from 1.5m to ~3m) pegmatites occurs along the foliation. These sets of
33 pegmatites show bifurcation and anastomosing geometry in places. In several places, the country
34 rocks occur as enclaves within the pegmatites (Fig. 8c). There is also a set of thin (thickness ~1.2cm)
35 pegmatites at a low angle to the general foliation, which shows crosscutting relationship with the
36 earlier set of pegmatites. The host rock contains a third set of 30cm to ~4m thick pegmatites at a
37 high angle to the major gneissic foliation.

38

39 **Text S3. Complex rheological properties of the model material**

40 The choice of the model material is crucial to simulate the natural process in a laboratory condition,
41 and it needs proper scaling to the natural prototype in regard to geometric, kinematic, and dynamic
42 parameters (Hubbert, 1937; Ramberg, 1981). Most of the previous workers used pure end-member
43 rheology for the host. However, the Earth's crust of the earth is not purely viscous or elastic, or
44 plastic. Rather, it behaves visco-elasto-plastically and accommodates the incoming fluid by hybrid
45 deformation (Rubin, 1993; Vachon & Hieronymus, 2016; Scheibert et al., 2017). The present
46 laboratory study thus used two complex rheological materials to represent the host. The first

47 material chosen for the experiments is Ultrasound Transmission Gel (*USTG*), which is available
48 commercially. A batch of *USTG* was procured from the market to ensure the material composition
49 and properties constant in the entire series of experiments. The *USTG* was mainly composed of
50 Carbopol powder and water. Carbopol gel is nowadays a widely used model material to mimic
51 crustal rheology, specifically the visco-elasto-plastic nature of the lower crustal rheology (Reber et
52 al., 2020). This gel is basically a combination of elastoplastic grains and fluid on a micro-scale
53 (Oppong & de Bruyn, 2011; Piau, 2007; Reber et al., 2020; Shafiei et al., 2018).

54 Semi-brittle deformation processes have been modeled using Carbopol gel (Birren & Reber,
55 2019; Reber et al., 2015). In addition to these optimum rheological properties, the transparency of
56 the gel made it perfect for the observation of the ongoing emplacement process in 3D. In gel form,
57 the material behaves like a non-linear power-law fluid following the Herschel-Bulkley model for
58 stress-strain rate approximation.

$$59 \quad \sigma = \sigma_y + K_y \dot{\epsilon}^n \quad \text{Eqn. (S1)}$$

60 The stress σ depends on the strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$, the flow index n , the consistency K_y , and the yield stress σ_y .
61 The rheological details are presented later in this section.

62 The experimental study used gel wax as another type of host material. This is composed of
63 mineral oil and hydrocarbon-based polymer. gel wax is a gelatine like material, which is widely used
64 in the analog experiments of dyke and sill emplacement (e.g., Canon-Tapia and Merle, 2006;
65 Hyndman & Alt, 1987; Kervyn et al., 2009; Rivalta et al., 2005). The gel wax rheology that represents
66 upper-crustal visco-elastic behavior can be described by a parallel combination of spring and
67 dashpot.

68 The rheology of the *USTG* used in this study depends on the water / carbopol powder ratio,
69 and the pH of the water. On the other hand, the rheology of the Gel wax depends on the
70 concentration of the mineral oil. To find the rheological parameters of the present concern, their
71 rheological tests were performed in Anton Paar Modular Compact Rheometer 302e (Fig. S1).

72 **Figure S1.** Laboratory setup (Anton Paar Modular Compact Rheometer 302e) used for the
73 rheological tests of experimental model materials.

74 As the overall property of these two materials was known as visco-elasto-plastic and visco-elastic,
75 the rheological study ran oscillatory tests, also known as Dynamic Mechanical Analysis, which is ideal
76 for these types of material analysis. Two types of oscillatory tests: a) Amplitude sweeps and b)
77 Frequency sweep, were conducted.

78 ***a) Amplitude sweeps:***

79 These are the oscillatory tests where the amplitude varies, keeping the frequency constant. For
80 controlled shear strain, $\gamma(t) = \gamma_A \sin \omega t$ where, γ_A is the shear strain amplitude (in %), ω is the angular
81 frequency (s^{-1}), which was held constant, and t represents run time. (Fig. S2)

82

83
 84 **Figure S2.** Oscillating strain (γ) imposed in the rheometer at a constant angular frequency same
 85 (after Mezger, 2014) in the amplitude test of rheology.

86
 87 Similarly, for controlled shear stress, $\tau(t) = \tau_A \sin\omega t$ where τ_A is the shear stress amplitude (in %).

88 ***b) Frequency sweeps:***

89 These are oscillatory tests where the strain amplitude remains constant, whereas the frequency
 90 changes with time. For tests with controlled shear strain, $\gamma(t) = \gamma_A \sin\omega t$ with $\gamma_A = \text{constant}$ and a
 91 variable angular frequency $\omega = \omega(t)$, where the period of oscillation cycles either increases or
 92 decreases continuously (Fig. S3).

93
 94 **Figure S3.** Strain test with varying angular frequency with time, keeping a constant strain amplitude
 95 (after Mezger, 2014)

96 Similarly, tests with controlled shear stress: $\tau(t) = \tau_A \sin\omega t$, with $\tau_A = \text{constant}$ and $\omega = \omega(t)$ are run
97 with varying period.

98 ***Rheological analysis of Gel Wax: Results***

99 The rheological tests reveal that the gel wax used in this study is viscoelastic. Its storage
100 modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') (Mezger, 2014) show systematic variations with increasing strain
101 (Fig. S4) and stress (Fig. 2c). The material behaviour describes a *linear viscoelastic (LVE)* regime below
102 a threshold state (yield point, γ_y). In the *LVE* regime G' remains constant with increasing strain, and
103 always maintains the following condition: $G' > G''$. At (yield point, γ_y), G' begins to decline, describing
104 a nonlinear viscoelastic (*NLVE*) regime, and the material ultimately undergoes fracture failure at a
105 critical strain defined by the crossover between G' and G'' values (Fig. S4).

106

107 **Figure S4.** Results of strain sweep tests run on gel Wax. Note that G' (storage modulus) $>$ G'' (loss
108 modulus), implying its viscoelastic solid rheology.

109 ***Rheological analysis of USTG: Results***

110 The *USTG* tests show similar viscoelastic rheology, describing a *LVE* and a *NLVE* regime with their
111 transition at the yield point (γ_y) (Fig. S5 & 2b). Unlike gel wax, this material had relatively gentle
112 decline of the storage modulus (G') with strain to attain the cross-over point (γ_f), indicating plastic
113 failure in the material.

114

115 **Figure S5.** Strain sweep test result for *USTG*.

116 ***Rheological comparison between USTG and Gel wax***

117 The graphical plots of G' and G'' as a function of stress and strain, presented in Fig 2b and c and Fig.
 118 S4 & S5, respectively, show a rheological similarity between *USTG* and gel wax with $G' \gg G''$ (for
 119 *USTG*, $G' \sim 19$ times G'' and for gel wax, $G' \sim 36$ times G'') in the *LVE* range. Beyond the yield point (τ_y),
 120 both *USTG* ($\tau_y = 3.84$ Pa) and gel wax ($\tau_y = 499$ Pa) show similar behavior in the *NLVE* range,
 121 characterized by a distinct drop of G' and counter rise of G'' . However, there is a difference in their
 122 failure behavior, which is evident from Fig. 2b & c. The *USTG* fails plastically at $\tau_f = 100$ Pa ($G' = G'' \sim 79$
 123 Pa) marked by a gradual drop of both G' and G'' . In contrast, the gel wax undergoes fracture failure
 124 at $\tau_f = 6209$ Pa ($G' = G'' \sim 1850$ Pa) following sharp drops of both G' and G'' .

125 In the present experiments the stress levels lie in the range beginning from ~ 15 Pa and ~ 667
 126 Pa to the failure points for *USTG* and gel wax respectively (Fig. b & c), implying that the experiments
 127 were run entirely in the *NLVE* rheological regime. The stress conditions in the experiments with
 128 *USTG* and gel wax hosts, normalized to their respective *NLVE* ranges ($\tau_f - \tau_y = 94$ Pa and 5710 Pa) fall
 129 broadly in the same ranges, 0.15 to 1.04 (*USTG*) and 0.12 to 1.09. These estimates suggest dynamic
 130 similarity of intrusion experiments with the two kinds of host materials.

131 ***Rheological analysis of hair oil: Results***

132 We used commercial hair oil as an analogue intruding liquid in the experiment. A rotational flow test
 133 was performed in the Rheometer to analyse the viscous rheology of the oil. The test yields a linear
 134 stress versus strain rate relation (Fig. S4), implying that this is a Newtonian liquid.

135
 136 **Figure S4.** Result of rotation tests on hair oil used as analog magma liquid in the laboratory
 137 experiments. *Left:* Plots of stress versus strain rate, showing a typical linear curve for Newtonian
 138 viscous rheology. *Right:* Strain-rate independent viscosity (η in mPa) of the liquid.

139
 140 **Text S4: Model scaling**

141 To scale the model to nature, the methods developed in earlier studies (Hubbert, 1937, Merle and
 142 Borgia, 1996, Merle, 2015, and Arachchige et al., 2022) were used. An approximate geometric,
 143 kinematic, and dynamic similarity between the model and natural was considered in terms of scaling
 144 factors and dimensionless numbers, as explained below.

145 The length scale factor is defined by the ratio between the intrusion dimension in model
 146 (l_M) to that in nature (l_N). The present modelling sets a scale where 1 cm in the model is equivalent
 147 to 10000 cm or 100 m in nature. The length scaling factor thus follows,

148
$$L^* = \frac{l_M}{l_N} = 10^{-4} \tag{Eqn. (S2)}$$

149 Now, comparing the average model intrusion velocity (v_M) with that nature (v_N) available in
 150 literature (see Table 1), the velocity scaling factor, v^* is estimated in the range 10^{-1} - 10^{-2} . The time
 151 scaling factor is then found in the range,

152
$$t^* = \frac{L^*}{v^*} = \frac{10^{-4}}{10^{-1}} = 10^{-3} \text{ to } \frac{10^{-4}}{10^{-2}} = 10^{-2}. \tag{Eqn. (S3)}$$

153 The volumetric flow rate (VFR) of magma intrusions in nature varies from $5.62 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $179 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$
 154 (Table 1), whereas the model VFR ranges from $10^{-7} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $1.67 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. From the scaling factor of
 155 length (L^*) and time (t^*) in Eqns. (S2) and (S3), the VFR scaling factor is calculated as,

$$156 \frac{VFR_M}{VFR_N} = VFR^* = \frac{(L^*)^3}{t^*} = \frac{(10^{-4})^3}{10^{-3}} = 10^{-9} \text{ to } \frac{(10^{-4})^3}{10^{-2}} = 10^{-10}. \quad \text{Eqn. (S4)}$$

157 The model VFR^* values (10^{-8} to 10^{-9}) are consistent with the value range obtained from Eqn. S4.

158 And the stress (dynamic) scaling factor is:

$$159 \sigma^* = \rho_h \times g \times L^* \sim 10^{-5}, \quad \text{Eqn. (S5)}$$

160 The dynamic factor in Eqn. S5 implies that the laboratory model is 10^5 times weaker than the natural
 161 counterpart. This ratio satisfies the scale down laws proposed by Hubbert (1937).

162 Using the Buckingham- Π theorem (Galland et al., 2009, Merle, 2015, and Arachchige et al., 2022), six
 163 independent dimensionless numbers are chosen to describe the experimental system (Table 1).

164 The length scale factor in Eq. S2 yields the inlet diameter ratios for nature in the range,

$$165 \Pi_1 = \frac{L^*}{d_N} = \frac{10^3}{10^{-1}} = 10^4 \text{ to } \frac{10^3}{5 \times 10^4} = 2 \times 10^{-2}. \quad \text{Eqn. (S6)}$$

166 For the present experiments,

$$167 \Pi_1 = \frac{L^*}{d_M} = \frac{2 \times 10^{-1}}{8 \times 10^{-3}} = 31.25, \quad \text{Eqn. (S7)}$$

168 which falls well within the limiting values in Eq. S3.

169 Intrusion thickness (T) in nature and in the experiments varies from 20 m–200 m and 2 mm to 2 cm,
 170 respectively. The model to nature thickness ratio (T^*) thus follows,

$$171 \frac{T_M}{T_N} = \frac{0.002}{20} = 10^{-4} \text{ to } \frac{0.02}{200} = 10^{-4} \quad \text{Eqn. (S8)}$$

172 The second dimensionless geometric term calculated from Eqn. S8 and S2 is

$$173 \Pi_2 = \frac{L^*}{T^*} = 1, \quad \text{Eqn. (S9)}$$

174 Eqn. S9 implies a good match with the natural prototype.

175 The third dimensionless number is expressed as,

$$176 \Pi_3 = \frac{\text{Depth of Intrusion (H)}}{\text{Intrusion Thickness (T)}} \quad \text{Eqn. (S10)}$$

177 For nature, Eqn. S10 yields,

178 $\Pi_3 = \frac{H}{T} = \frac{100}{200} = 0.5 \text{ to } \frac{3000}{20} = 150$ and Eqn. (S11)

179 for present study,

180 $\Pi_3 = \frac{0.07}{0.002} = 3.5 \text{ to } \frac{0.07}{0.02} = 35$ Eqn. (S12)

181 The Π_3 values for experiment in Eqn. S12 lie within the range of values calculated for nature from
182 Eqn. S11.

183 Fourth dimensionless number for the inertial term is given by,

184 $\Pi_4 = L^* \times (t^*)^{-2} = 10^{-4} \times (10^{-2})^{-2} = 1$, Eqn. (S13)

185 Fifth non-dimensional number related to buoyancy of magma is defined by the ratio of hydrostatic
186 and lithostatic forces, indicated by Galland et al. (2009):

187 $\Pi_5 = 1 - \frac{\rho_i}{\rho_h}$ Eqn. (S14)

188 In natural condition Π_5 varies between -0.8 to 0 and the calculation from Eqn. S14 yield the value for
189 the present experimental condition as,

190 *USTG-Oil*: $\Pi_5 = 1 - \frac{880}{1270} = 0.307$ Eqn. (S15)

191 *USTG-water*: $\Pi_5 = 1 - \frac{997.7}{1270} = 0.214$ Eqn. (S16)

192 *Gel wax-water*: $\Pi_5 = 1 - \frac{997.7}{720.6} = -0.385$ Eqn. (S17)

193 From Eqn. 15, 16 and 17 it is evident that in two cases the magma is a little bit buoyant, as also found
194 in earlier studies, e.g., Arachchige et al., 2022. However, from the calculation of stokes velocity for
195 buoyancy it is found that the velocity due to buoyancy is negligible in the present experimental
196 condition, detail discussion in Text S7.

197 The sixth non-dimensional number is defined by the viscosity ratio between the host and the
198 intrusion. As described below,

199 $\Pi_6 = \frac{\text{Viscosity of the host } (\eta_{\text{host}})}{\text{Viscosity of the melt } (\eta_{\text{melt}})}$ Eqn. (S18)

200 In nature Π_6 calculated from Eqn. S18 varies from 10^{-10} to 10^{23} , and in case of our experiment it varies
201 from 10^5 to 10^9 , which is well within the natural limits.

202

203 **Text S5. Péclet Number calculation for experimental intrusive flows**

204 The *Péclet number* (Pe) represents the ratio of heat transfer by fluid advection to heat transfer
205 through thermal conduction, expressed as,

$$206 \quad Pe = \frac{vL}{\kappa}, \quad \text{Eqn. (S19)}$$

207 where v is the average fluid flow velocity, L is a characteristic length scale (typically the flow
208 thickness), and κ is the thermal diffusivity of the fluid. $Pe \gg 1$ indicates that the fluid flows fast
209 enough to carry its heat with negligible heat dissipation by conduction. In contrast, for $Pe \ll 1$ the
210 fluid will flow at slow rates, allowing its cooling by heat conduction that can result in solidification
211 before the fluid flows on a long distance. The present study accounts for this dimensionless
212 parameter, as described below.

213 In case of the present experimental condition, the flow velocity (v) varies in the following range:

$$214 \quad v_{min} = 1.99 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ to } v_{max} = 3.32 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m s}^{-1}.$$

215 The thermal diffusivities (κ) of intrusion liquids used in the experiments are:

$$216 \quad \text{Water: } \kappa_{water} = 1.43 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ at } 25^\circ\text{C} \text{ (Raj et al., 2020).}$$

$$217 \quad \text{Oil: } \kappa_{oil} = 2.75 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ (Raj et al., 2021)}$$

218 Considering the intrusion diameter as a characteristic length (8×10^{-3} m), the Pe calculations yield
219 $Pe_{water} = 111.3$ to 1857 , and $Pe_{oil} = 57.9$ to 965.8 . The calculated $Pe \gg 1$ conditions for both water
220 and oil indicate that the liquid intrusion in experiments is fast enough to advect heat dominating
221 over the conduction, and that the kinematic condition simulates sub-surface magmatic intrusions
222 without significant solidification during the flows.

223

224 **Text S6. Method of 2-D fractal dimension calculation**

225 A fractal analysis was performed to characterize irregular host-intrusive interfaces observed in the
226 field and laboratory models. A fractal set of objects can be defined as,

$$227 \quad N = \frac{C}{r^D} \quad \text{Eqn. (S20)}$$

228 where N is the number of objects with linear dimension r , C is the proportionality constant, and D is
229 the fractal dimension. In equation (20), N holds a power law relation with r , and their distribution on
230 a log space shows essentially a linear regression.

231 The images of intrusives taken in the field and during the experiments were used to
232 calculate the fractal dimension of interfaces between the host and magma. During the image

233 accusation of experimental models, special care was taken to eliminate the effects of various light-
234 related phenomena, e.g., light refraction and diffraction. All the cameras were set normal to three
235 principal sides, i.e., XY , XZ , and YZ , glass plate used in box making was chosen very thin (0.1 mm) to
236 exclude any effect of refraction (Fig. 2a). On the other hand, to reduce the diffraction effects, the
237 illumination setup in the laboratory used LED light with a diffuser from four sides with almost equal
238 intensity. This type of illumination setup kept the intensity of reflected light much stronger than that
239 of the diffracted light and, also reduces both temporal and spatial phase differences. In addition, the
240 camera apertures were set at their highest extent (f-stop: 3.6) during the image capturing to
241 minimize the diffraction effect.

242 In the next step, the host-intrusion boundaries were tracked from the experimental models
243 and field photographs using MATLAB. The boundaries in a RGB format were then converted to
244 binary images, which were used for the calculations of 2D fractal dimensions using the '*boxcount*'
245 function in the MATLAB environment (Fig. S6).

246 Details of '*boxcount*': (<http://www.fast.u-psud.fr/~moisy/ml/boxcount/html/demo.html>).

247

248 **Figure S6.** Matching fractal dimensions were found for both the field sample (*left column*) and
249 experimental models (*right column*).

250

251 **Text S7. Buoyancy-driven flow: Stokes velocity calculation**

252 The velocity of a spherical low-viscosity fluid body ascending through a high-viscosity fluid host
253 under buoyancy is given by,

254
$$U = \frac{a^2 g \Delta \rho}{3 \mu_f}, \quad \text{Eqn. (S21)}$$

255 where a is the radius of the spherical body, g is the acceleration due to gravity, $\Delta \rho$ stands for the
256 density difference between the host and the ascending body, and μ_f is the host fluid viscosity. The
257 buoyancy driven flow velocities calculated from Equation (S21) are presented below.

258 *Gel wax-water* combination: $U = \frac{(0.4 \times 10^{-3})^2 \times 9.8 \times 279.4}{3 \times 10^6} = 1.46 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-1}$.

259 *USTG-water* combination: $U = \frac{(0.4 \times 10^{-3})^2 \times 9.8 \times 270}{3 \times 10^3} = 1.41 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m s}^{-1}$.

260 For *USTG-oil* combination: $U = \frac{(0.4 \times 10^{-3})^2 \times 9.8 \times 390}{3 \times 10^3} = 2.04 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m s}^{-1}$.

261 These estimates suggest that the flux-driven intrusion velocity (in the order of $10^{-2} - 10^{-3} \text{ m s}^{-1}$) far
262 exceeds the buoyancy driven flow velocities, which lie in the range of 10^{-7} to $10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-1}$. The latter
263 had little effects on the experimental intrusion patterns produced on the intrusion time scales in
264 laboratory.

265

266 **Text S8. The procedure of Aspect Ratio (α) Calculation**

267 The calculation of the aspect ratio (α) of an intrusion-related protrusion into the host accounted for
268 the half wavelength (L) and the amplitude (H), which were measured by using *CorelDraw 2021*, as
269 shown in Fig. S7. The collected data are provided in the data repository (Biswas et al., 2023). It is to
270 note that the measured values do not represent the real scale dimensions. As α is the ratio of L to H ,
271 the scale of measurement hardly affects the analysis of this parameter. The measurements were,
272 however, carefully conducted from undistorted photographic images of intrusive bodies.

273

274 **Figure S7.** The procedure of Aspect Ratio (a) calculations.

275

276 **Text S9.** The procedure of Skewness and Kurtosis Calculation

277

278 **Figure S8.** The boundary between the host and the intrusion was reconstructed using MATLAB for
 279 skewness-kurtosis calculations.

280

281 **Figure S9.** Flow chart of the procedure steps for calculations of skewness and kurtosis of irregular
282 intrusion boundaries.

283

285

286 **Figure S10.** (a) Dike in CGGC showing branching at a very high angle (~90°), (b) Sharp boundary
287 pure fracture dominated dike in the field, Purulia, West Bengal., and (c) Networking of small-scale
288 dikes in the field.

289 **References**

290 • Arachchige, U. N., Cruden, A. R., Weinberg, R., Slim, A., & Köpping, J. (2022). Saucers, Fingers, and
291 Lobes: New Insights on Sill Emplacement From Scaled Laboratory Experiments. *Journal of*
292 *Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 127(11), e2022JB024421.
293 • Birren, T., Reber, J.E., 2019. The impact of rheology on the transition from stick-slip to creep in a semi-
294 brittle analog. *J. Geophys. Res. Solid Earth* 124 (3), 3144–3154.
295 • Biswas, Uddalak; Mitra, Atin Kumar; Mandal, Nibir (2023), Data for: Wall fracturing versus mechanical
296 instability as competing intrusion mechanisms of dikes: Insights from laboratory experiments, Dryad,
297 Dataset, <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.3r2280gmv>
298 • Canon-Tapia, E., Merle, O., 2006. Dyke nucleation and early growth from pressurized magma
299 chambers: Insights from analog models. *J. Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.* 158 (3–4), 207–220.
300 • Galland, Olivier, Planke, S., Neumann, E. R., & Malthe-Sørensen, A. (2009). Experimental modelling of
301 shallow magma emplacement: Application to saucer-shaped intrusions. *Earth and Planetary Science*
302 *Letters*, 277(3–4), 373–383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EPSL.2008.11.003>

- 303 • Hayman, N.W., Ducloue, L., Foco, K.L., Daniels, K.E., 2011. Granular controls on periodicity of stick-slip
304 events: kinematics and force-chains in an experimental fault. *Pure Appl. Geophys.* 168 (12), 2239–
305 2257.
- 306 • Hubbert, M.K., Theory of scale models as applied to the study of geologic structures, *Geol. Soc.*
307 *Amer. Bull.* 48 (1937) 1459–1520.
- 308 • Kervyn, M., Ernst, G.G.J., de Vries, B.V., Mathieu, L., Jacobs, P., 2009. Volcano load control on dyke
309 propagation and vent distribution: Insights from analog modeling. *J. Geophys. Res. Solid Earth* 114.
- 310 • Merle, O., & Borgia, A. (1996). Scaled experiments of volcanic spreading. *Journal of Geophysical*
311 *Research: Solid Earth*, 101(B6), 13805-13817.
- 312 • Merle, O. (2015). The scaling of experiments on volcanic systems. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 3, 26.
- 313 • Mezger, T.G., *The Rheology Handbook*, Vincentz Network, Hanover, Germany, 2014, ISBN 978-3-
314 86630-650-9
- 315 • Oppong, F.K., de Bruyn, J.R., 2011. Microrheology and jamming in a yield-stress fluid. *Rheol. Acta* 50
316 (4), 317–326.
- 317 • Piau, J.M., 2007. Carbopol gels: Elastoviscoplastic and slippery glasses made of individual swollen
318 sponges. Meso- and macroscopic properties, constitutive equations, and scaling laws. *J. Non-*
319 *Newtonian Fluid Mech.* 144 (1), 1–29.
- 320 • Raj V, Swapna MNS, Sankararaman SI. Criticality of depth of intensity modulation
321 and simulation of refractive index profile in thermal lens technique. *Eur*
322 *Phys J Appl Phys* 2020;90:11001. <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjap/2020200024>.
- 323 • Raj, V., Swapna, M. S., & Sankararaman, S. (2022). Acclimatization through thermal diffusivity tuning
324 of coconut oil–A mode mismatched dual-beam thermal lens study. *Journal of Ayurveda and*
325 *Integrative Medicine*, 13(2), 100502.
- 326 • Ramberg, H., *Gravity, deformation and the Earth's crust*, Academic Press, New York, 1981, 452 pp.
- 327 • Reber, J. E., Cooke, M. L., & Dooley, T. P. (2020). What model material to use? A Review on rock analogs
328 for structural geology and tectonics. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 202, 103107.
- 329 • Reber, J.E., Lavier, L.L., Hayman, N.W., 2015. Experimental demonstration of a semi-brittle origin for
330 crustal strain transients. *Nat. Geosci.* 8 (9), 712.
- 331 • Rivalta, E., Bottinger, M., Dahm, T., 2005. Buoyancy-driven fracture ascent: Experiments in layered
332 gelatine. *J. Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.* 144 (1–4), 273–285.
- 333 • Rubin, A. (1993). Dikes vs. diapirs in viscoelastic rock. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 119, 641–659.
- 334 • Scheibert, J., Galland, O., and Hafver, A. (2017). Inelastic deformation during sill and laccolith
335 emplacement: insights from an analytic elastoplastic model. *J. Geophys. Res. Solid Earth* 122, 923–
336 945. doi: 10.1002/2016JB013754
- 337 • Shafiei, M., Balhoff, M., Hayman, N.W., 2018. Chemical and microstructural controls on viscoplasticity
338 in Carbopol hydrogel. *Polymer* 139, 44–51.
- 339 • Vachon, R., and Hieronymus, C. F. (2016). Effect of host-rock rheology on dike shape, thickness, and
340 magma overpressure. *Geophys. J. Int.* 208, 1414–1429. doi: 10.1093/gji/ggw448